

Demand Planning in Fashion Retail: A Practitioner Framework Linking Top-Down and Bottom-Up Forecasting

Merchandise Planning and Operational Forecasting

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Abstract

Demand planning is a core capability in fashion and consumer goods companies, connecting commercial expectations with supply execution and inventory investment. This practitioner paper introduces the fundamentals of demand planning (often referred to as merchandise planning or operational forecasting) and outlines how planning teams translate sales expectations into purchase budgets and unit demand. The discussion contrasts top-down and bottom-up methodologies and explains how the choice of approach depends on the availability and reliability of historical sell-out and sell-in data. Key planning elements are reviewed, including product mix, markdown assumptions, leftover planning, cancellations and delays, returns in online channels, assortment requirements, rate-of-sale estimation, initial allocation, sizing, and carry-over management. Finally, the paper describes the reconciliation loop required when bottom-up forecasts and top-down targets diverge, and highlights the role of analytics and machine learning in improving forecast accuracy.

Keywords: Demand planning, Merchandise planning, Operational forecasting, Fashion retail, Inventory management, Top-down forecasting, Bottom-up forecasting, Sell-in, Sell-out, Open-to-Buy (OTB), WSSI, Assortment planning, Allocation, Replenishment, Markdown, Returns, Machine learning

Author note: This paper is written from a practitioner perspective and is intended for executives, practitioners, and students. The views expressed are the author's own and do not necessarily represent those of any employer.

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1. Introduction: What Is Demand Planning?

Demand planning—often referred to as merchandise planning or operational forecasting—is the activity of determining how much inventory is required to satisfy future customer demand. It is a critical process in fashion companies and in many other industries because it links sales expectations to production and supply decisions.

Operational forecasts represent the best estimate of future outcomes: an expectation of what is **likely to happen**. This differs from **targets** (for example, sales targets or financial targets), which describe what an organization **would like** to achieve and therefore represent an aspiration rather than an expectation.

2. Top-Down and Bottom-Up Planning Approaches

A demand forecast may start either from high-level assumptions (for example, total company, market, or channel) or from the lowest level (for example, aggregating forecasts for individual products or SKUs). A robust planning process typically combines top-down and bottom-up methodologies to enable consistency checks and to capture the benefits of both exercises.

Top-down exercises include purchase budget definition, Open-to-Buy (OTB), target setting, and Weekly Sales Stock Inventory (WSSI). Bottom-up exercises start from the forecast of a single product—at SKU level (Stock Keeping Unit) or product level—and build upward through item plans, range plans, and rate-of-sale models.

3. Data Availability and Choice of Methodology

Method selection depends largely on the availability and quality of historical data, particularly sell-in and sell-out. Sell-in refers to shipments from a company to a store or to a third-party customer. Sell-out refers to sales to the final consumer, either through a company-owned network (DTC—Direct-to-Consumer) or through a wholesale partner.

Planning based on sell-out is generally preferable because it reflects consumer demand. If sell-out information is unavailable or not sufficiently reliable, forecasting based on sell-in provides a practical alternative.

4. Top-Down Demand Planning

4.1 Top-down planning based on sell-out

Top-down planning based on sell-out starts by estimating the net sales value expected for the relevant country or channel over a defined time horizon (for example, a season, half-year, quarter, or year). A common approach is to apply an expected growth rate versus last year when the prior-year baseline is comparable (like-for-like, LFL). This assumption should be aligned with commercial leadership. For new openings, expected revenues defined during store approval can be used, or the revenue of a comparable store can serve as a proxy.

More advanced models may leverage statistical forecasting, regression, machine learning, or related techniques to estimate likely sell-out for the upcoming season. In many fashion organizations, the core planning horizon is seasonal (Spring/Summer and Fall/Winter), typically covering about six months, although planning cadences may vary by company.

Once total sell-out is defined, the forecast is translated into product categories through a product mix (for example, tops versus bottoms, or sub-categories such as graphic tees versus shirts). The mix should be evaluated alongside absolute variation versus the previous season, particularly for small categories where small percentage changes may translate into meaningful value changes. The mix typically starts with historical results and is refined using: (i) latest product trends (including current season sell-through and broader trends), (ii) planned marketing investments, and (iii) feedback on the new collection.

Fashion planning often includes an explicit assumption for leftover (planned unsold inventory at full price), reflecting forecast inaccuracy and the economics of end-of-season liquidation. Industries with rapid obsolescence (for example, some technology categories) may plan purchases closer to expected sales, while fashion often plans some extra stock that may later be sold through outlets or off-price channels. As a rule of thumb, premium brands may plan higher leftover than fast-fashion brands, which typically operate with higher sell-through.

In addition to net sales and leftover, markdown assumptions are critical. Markdown represents the difference between the recommended retail price (RRP) and the realized selling price (AUR—Average Unit Retail). Top-down planning should incorporate expected markdowns based on historical performance and planned optimization to support gross margin.

Operational realities should also be incorporated, including limited supply chain cancellations or delays. In online channels, consumer returns can be a major driver of gross demand. Returns may range widely by country and product type; therefore, planning should focus on net sales (net of returns) and include an explicit provision for returns.

Summary relationship (illustrative):

Purchase Budget (value) = Net Sales + Markdowns + Leftover (+ Cancellations/Delays)

Once the purchase budget is defined in value, it can be translated into units by dividing by an assumed average unit cost or price, depending on the planning convention.

4.2 Top-down planning based on sell-in

If sell-out data are unavailable, top-down planning can be built from historical shipments (sell-in). Expected growth or decline assumptions should be developed jointly with commercial teams to reflect customer knowledge and market context. Wholesale orders may be driven by pre-season firm orders (often referred to as pre-book/pre-buy) and by in-season replenishment. Firm pre-season orders increase forecast certainty and reduce production risk. Where commitments are non-binding, there is a risk that customers will deviate from stated intentions.

In-season replenishment is typically planned by the producing company for core product, informed by historical patterns.

Top-down outputs generally define targets at category and/or customer level and serve as the reference point for bottom-up planning.

5. Bottom-Up Demand Planning

5.1 Bottom-up planning based on sell-out

Bottom-up planning requires a defined product assortment, typically provided by buying or merchandising teams. A complete assortment typically includes: product attributes (gender/category/story and reference items), lifecycle phasing (start date, full-price period), price and cost, distribution intent (door coverage, accounts/segments), marketing/merchandising focus, and a commercial ranking of products.

A common bottom-up calculation is:

$$\text{Demand (units)} = (\text{APS} \times \text{Weeks} \times \text{Doors}) \div \text{Sell-through\%}$$

Where APS (Average Per Store) or Rate of Sale represents average weekly sell-out per door; Weeks is the number of full-price selling weeks; Doors is the number of stores or customers; and Sell-through% represents the expected ratio of full-price sales to total shipments.

Weeks and Doors are typically straightforward to define. Sell-through% depends on pricing strategy and expected timing of markdowns. Seasonal product may target partial sell-through before markdown periods, while a 100% target implies selling out before markdown. For carry-over products that continue into the following season, sell-through assumptions are treated differently because the inventory remains available beyond the season.

The most critical variable is APS, which is often estimated using comparable product history and merchant rankings. APS estimation may range from simple analog methods to statistical and machine-learning approaches. Advanced methods can improve forecast quality by considering multiple demand drivers and identifying the most likely sales scenario.

More refined bottom-up approaches incorporate beginning-of-period and end-of-period inventory for carry-over items (BOP/EOP or BOM/EOM, depending on the planning cadence).

Additional bottom-up considerations include: initial allocation (the first shipment to stores, which sets a minimum forecast), size coverage (at least one unit per planned store for each selected size), and marketing/window requirements (units needed for display, uniforms, or campaign execution).

5.2 Bottom-up planning based on sell-in

When sell-out data are not available, bottom-up planning can be based on historical shipments for similar products. A common approach is to use matrix-based analogs to set expectations for

high/medium/low performers within a category or segment. Statistical and machine-learning methods can also be used and may incorporate missed demand due to prior stock-outs.

Wholesale demand should reflect both pre-book (pre-season) and replenishment (in-season) components. Two approaches are commonly applied: (i) estimate total demand and split between pre-book and replenishment using historical patterns, or (ii) plan pre-book and replenishment separately in parallel.

6. Reconciling Bottom-Up Forecasts and Top-Down Targets

After bottom-up forecasts are finalized, they are compared with the targets produced by top-down planning. If the forecasts align, the plan is internally consistent. In practice, divergence is common and triggers an iterative revision process.

If bottom-up is lower than top-down, potential actions include reassessing APS assumptions (to test whether they are overly conservative), reviewing option counts and assortment breadth, and revisiting category/sub-category budget splits. If these levers are exhausted, top-down targets may require recalibration.

If bottom-up is higher than top-down, potential actions include reassessing APS assumptions (to test whether they are overly optimistic), reviewing option counts versus space and budget constraints, and revisiting category/sub-category budget splits. If these levers are exhausted, top-down targets may be too low relative to opportunity.

At the end of the iteration, top-down and bottom-up forecasts should converge. The reconciled forecast may then be phased by month or week to support supply planning, reflecting store needs and historical seasonality.

7. Final Considerations

Demand planning is iterative and requires continuous monitoring of sales trends and forecast accuracy. Forecasts will not be perfectly accurate; however, strong planning processes and tools can reduce errors and support a healthy balance between sales growth and inventory investment.

References (selected)

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